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BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

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Eco-friendly fabrication of graphene from apple biomass precursor*S. Dorontić^{1*}, S. Jovanović¹**(1) Vinča Institute of Nuclear Sciences - National Institute of the Republic of Serbia, University of Belgrade P.O. Box 522, 11001 Belgrade, Serbia;***sladjana.dorontic@vin.bg.ac.rs*

Graphene is a two-dimensional carbon nanomaterial, consisting of sp^2 hybridized carbon atoms, organized in a honeycomb hexagonal crystal lattice [1]. Due to their extraordinary physical and chemical properties such as high electrical conductivity of $10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ V}^{-1} \text{ s}^{-1}$, Young's module close to 1 TPa, as well as large surface area ($2630 \text{ m}^2 \text{ g}^{-1}$), they attract the attention of researchers from science toward industry.

Graphene can be produced by different techniques such as chemical synthesis, chemical, mechanical or electrochemical exfoliation, thermal annealing, etc. Synthesis of graphene in that way usually includes the consumption of commercially available chemicals. To avoid disadvantages, researchers developed methods based on biomass and bio-waste materials for graphene synthesis [2]. Within these procedures, starting materials for graphene synthesis are wood parts [3], agricultural waste [4], fruits [5], and many others [2]. The main principle of graphene fabrication from biomass-derived sources consists of their pyrolysis under an inert atmosphere. Pyrolysis can be occurred on Cu support, in the presence of some activation agents such as base and salts, or in hydrothermal conditions. Activation agents lead to cutting, pore formation, and starting material exfoliation. KOH is an often used agent for activation. K^+ from KOH reacts with graphite microcrystals during the reaction by transferring a charge to the [graphene-H]⁻ complex. H atoms became removed from the complex, which cause the formation of sp^2 atoms. Also, the presence of KOH released CO_2 in reaction penetrates between graphene layers, separating them, and increasing the surface of the material [2].

Apple and products made of them are the most consumed fruit and products all over the world [6]. According to the Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Water Economy of the Republic of Serbia data, $26.1 \times 10^6 \text{ L}$ of fruit alcohol drinks including apple-based ones, were produced in 2021 [7]. Large amounts of solid and liquid apple wastes are generated during the apple processing [6]. Per each liter of produced fruit alcohol, around 8–15 L of wastewater (stillage) is produced. Due to high biodegradability, that waste has become a great environmental problem. Most of the waste goes to landfill, is burned, and contribute to an increase in the amount of greenhouse gases. It also reaches aquatic ecosystems, causing their eutrophication. Apple biomass and bio-waste were investigated as start carbon material for graphene production in many reported researches [8, 9].

In this study, graphene-like material was synthesized from biomass obtained during the apple alcohol drink preparation process. Raw biowaste was dried to the powder and mixed with KOH pastilles to create a homogenous powder. Then, the mixture was heated in the furnace at $850 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 1 hour, under an atmosphere of inert gas. After heating, the material was washed from KOH, until pH reached neutral. The structure of produced material was investigated using infrared spectroscopy with Fourier transformation (FTIR) and Raman spectroscopy. The structural analysis confirmed the presence of the graphene domains in biomass-derived material.

Stillage obtained from appleschnapps is a possible starting material in graphene fabrication. Thanks to low prices, eco-friendly, sustainable, and simple approach, as well as increasing graphene market, the presented method has a huge potential to become an important method in graphene production.

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